

THE INFLUENCE OF MATRIX PLASTICITY ON THE FAILURE STRAIN OF TRANSVERSELY LOADED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The influence of the matrix on the transverse tensile properties of unidirectional fibre reinforced composites is investigated on carbon fibre reinforced composites, based on epoxy matrices with various failure strains. Experiments indicate that an increase in matrix failure strain yields a relatively low increase in composite's transverse failure strain. Finite Element Micromechanical Analyses are used to compare the deformation of the matrix in transversely loaded fibre reinforced plastics with the deformation in rubber toughened plastics. The analyses showed that the stress situation in fibre reinforced composites leads to a brittle behaviour even with very ductile matrices, whereas the stress situation in rubber toughened systems appears to be more favourable for obtaining a high failure strain with ductile matrices. Since the stress situation in transversely loaded composites with rubber coated fibres is quite similar to that of rubber toughened systems, it is expected that the combination of rubber coated fibres with a ductile matrix yields composites with high transverse failure strains.

Keywords: Composite materials, transverse strain, micromechanical modelling, matrix ductility, rubber coating.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent investigations on the interlaminar delamination energy of fibre reinforced composites, the matrix ductility appeared to have a complex effect on the composite's fracture toughness G_{IC} and G_{IIC} [1,2,3]. Unfortunately, the fracture toughness increases less than proportional with the matrix G_{IC} [1,2]. This is generally explained by constrained matrix deformation due to the presence of brittle fibres, premature failure due to poor fibre-matrix adhesion or by a reduction of matrix deformation around the crack-tip due to the rigid fibres [1,3]. Considering the observed phenomena of the influence of the matrix ductility on the delamination energy, also in transverse tension the composite's strain capacity might be reduced by the presence of the fibres.

In this investigation the influence of the matrix failure strain on the transverse tensile failure strain of fibre reinforced composites is determined. Carbon fibre reinforced epoxies,

with epoxy matrices varying in failure strain, are tested in transverse tension and three-point bending. To obtain a better understanding of the experimental results, finite element micromechanical analyses are used to compare the matrix deformation in transversely loaded carbon fibre reinforced plastics with the deformation of the matrix in rubber toughened plastics. Finally the analyses are used on other composite systems to find ways to improve the transverse tensile strain to failure by using ductile matrices.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The influence of the matrix failure strain on the transverse failure strain of unidirectional composites is examined on carbon fibre reinforced epoxies with a perfect fibre-matrix adhesion. In order to exclude the influence of fibre-matrix debonding, surface treated high strength carbon fibres (AKZO Tenax HTA 5131) have been used [4]. The failure strain of epoxies can be controlled by the cross-link density [5]. In this study the cross-link density of the epoxy matrix is systematically varied by using a combination of a 2-functional curing agent (diethyl aniline, DEA, Perstorp Analytical) and a 4-functional curing agent (diethyl toluene diamine, DETDA, Lonza Ltd.) with a standard 2-functional epoxy resin (diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A, DGEBA, Shell Epikote 828EL). Rubber additives, normally utilized for toughening of epoxy resins, are not used to exclude matrix morphology effects on the transverse properties.

Curing of DGEBA with the 4-functional curing agent DETDA yields an common epoxy matrix with a high cross-link density. By replacing a part of DETDA with the 2-functional curing agent DEA the epoxy matrix will be less cross-linked. Consequently, the cross-link density can be controlled by the amount of DEA added to epoxy resin. By varying the ratio DETDA/DEA, a variation in tensile elongation is obtained from 4.8% to 42.1% (Table 1), without affecting the Young's modulus.

Table 1. Tensile properties of the epoxy matrices.

DETTA/DEA ratio	Young's Mod. [GPa]	Ultimate Stress [MPa]	Ultimate Strain [%]
1/0	2.5	68.6	4.8
2/1	2.7	74.5	7.6
1/1	2.6	72.9	8.9
1/4	2.6	67.9	16.9
1/8	2.6	64.3	24.2
1/12	2.8	67.7	42.1

The epoxy systems listed in Table 1 have been used as a matrix material for 50 vol.% unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced composites, manufactured by filament winding. Transverse properties have been determined by tensile tests and three-point bending. Figure 1 shows the transverse failure strain of the different composites. The failure strain in three-point bending appears to be significantly higher than the strain determined by tensile testing, because failure in bending is less controlled by flaws in the composite materials. In both type of tests the transverse failure strain showed a significant increase with matrix failure strain, however, this increase is quite disappointing when compared with the increase

in failure strain of the pure matrix. While the matrix failure strain has increased nine times, the composite transverse failure strain has increased only two times.

Figure 1. Transverse strain to failure of carbon fibre reinforced epoxies.

3. MICROMECHANICAL ANALYSES

Micromechanical finite element models make a careful analysis of the stress situation within a composite possible and can provide fundamental knowledge on the influence of various material parameters on the transverse properties. From the experiments it was shown that matrices with a higher strain capacity do not lead to a proportional increase in the transverse failure strain of the carbon fibre reinforced epoxies. A second constituent i.e., the carbon fibres in the composites, appears to reduce the ductility of the material and leads to a more brittle behaviour. On the other hand, for rubber toughened epoxies the second constituent seems to induce plastic deformation and yields to tough behaviour. To gain fundamental insight in the different effects of both rigid and soft constituents on the material plasticity, the matrix deformation in a 50 vol.% carbon fibre reinforced composite will be compared with the matrix deformation in a 5 vol.% rubber toughened plastic.

Figure 2. Finite element models of (a) carbon fibre reinforced composite and (b) rubber toughened material.

The numerical analyses on the carbon fibre reinforced composite are based on a two-dimensional generalized plane-strain model of a cross-section of a unidirectional composite. By assuming a regular square packing array, the model geometry can be reduced to a repeating unit of a quarter fibre in a block of matrix (Figure 2a). The analyses on the rubber toughened material are based on a two-dimensional cylindrical model of a rubber sphere in a cylindrical matrix, using axi-symmetric elements (Figure 2b). Quadratic elements are used for both models to achieve accurate results. With linear elements a finer mesh is required, because of the high stress gradients expected at the interface [6]. The mechanical properties of the transversely isotropic carbon fibres are listed in Table 2 with the properties of the other materials. The matrix material is considered to be ideal elasto-plastic with a Von Mises yield criterion. Considering the high strains that might appear in the matrix, the finite element analyses are performed geometrically non-linear using the high strain plasticity options within the finite element program MARC. Since the finite element analyses are geometrical non-linear, loads have been applied with incremental strain steps.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of the materials.

Material		Carbon fibre	Glass fibre	Epoxy matrix	Rubber
Long. modulus	E_L	235GPa	-	-	-
Transv. modulus	E_T	20 GPa	-	-	-
Long. Poisson ratio	ν_{LT}	0.013	-	-	-
Transv.Poiss. ratio	ν_{TT}	0.25	-	-	-
Shear modulus	G_{LT}	18 GPa	-	-	-
Young's modulus	E	-	72 GPa	3.2 GPa	3.0 MPa
Poisson ratio	ν	-	0.22	0.37	0.499
Yield stress	σ	-	-	68 MPa	-

3.1 Analysis of a carbon fibre reinforced epoxy

The numerical analysis on the transversely loaded carbon fibre reinforced composite yielded a stress-strain curve as shown in Figure 3. When the plastic deformation initiates, the transverse response initially remains still linear because the plastic deformation is localized at a few sites (Figure 4a). This plastic deformation starts between the fibres in the vicinity of the 'poles'. With a small increase of the load, a second area arises along the fibre-matrix interface (Figure 4a). A further increase of the applied strain causes an expansion of the plastic deformed area, with high shear deformation at the fibre-matrix interface (Figure 4b). Additional increase of the load yields a non-linear behaviour, with a plastically deformed area across the whole cross-sectional area of the model (Figure 4c). The increase of the transverse composite strain is mainly obtained by shear deformation within this thin band through the composite, whereas the rest of the material is restrained from plastic deformation by the presence of the rigid fibre. With higher strains this area does not expand (Figure 4d), but leads to more shear deformation in the yielded band, especially at the fibre-matrix interface.

Since the plastically deformed area remains relatively small, even at low transverse composite strain levels, local plastic strains within the composite are rather high. This is also illustrated in Figure 3, showing the observed maximum in local plastic strain caused by the applied transverse strain. By assuming a failure criterion, which is based on a maximum matrix strain level, it can be concluded that for this carbon fibre reinforced composite a strong increase in matrix ductility will hardly result in an increase in composite failure strain.

Figure 3. Calculated stress-strain curve of carbon fibre reinforced composite with the observed maximum in local plastic strain.

Figure 4. Plastically deformed area in the carbon fibre reinforced composite at: (a) 0.93%, (b) 1.20%, (c) 1.47% and (d) 1.74% transverse strain.

3.2 Analysis on a rubber toughened epoxy

The micromechanical analysis on the tensile loaded rubber toughened material yielded a stress-strain curve as shown in Figure 5. Plastic deformation starts at low stress levels due to stress concentrations. Also with this material the tensile behaviour remains initially quite linear due to the localized plastic deformation at the 'equator' (Figure 6a). Moreover, also in this type of composite an increase of the applied strain causes an expansion of the plastically deformed area to a kind of shear-band across the material (Figure 6b). However, upon further loading this area will extend (Figure 6c) and eventually nearly the whole matrix will show plastic deformation (Figure 6d).

Since the rubber sphere does not prevent the expansion of the plastically deformed area, the local plastic strains observed in this material are significantly lower than those in the carbon fibre reinforced composite (Figure 5). An increase of the matrix ductility can therefore directly lead to an increase in composite failure strain, since matrix failure will initiate at higher strains levels.

Figure 5. Stress-strain curve of a rubber toughened material with the observed maximum in local plastic strain.

Figure 6. The plastically deformed area in the rubber toughened material at: (a) 1.7%, (b) 2.4%, (c) 4.0% and (d) 8.0% tensile strain.

3.3 Analyses of other fibre reinforced composites

Since a second constituent in a ductile matrix has such strong effect on the overall material properties, it is interesting to investigate the influence of different fibre materials on the composite performance. Additional analyses on glass, rubber and rubber coated fibre 'reinforced' composites have been performed. Figure 7 illustrates how the maximum in local plastic strain increases with the applied transverse strain. The rigid glass fibre appears to have a similar effect on matrix deformation as the carbon fibre, with requiring very high local strains for obtaining an increase in overall composite transverse strain. Although the morphology in the 50 vol.% rubber composite is considerably different from the 5 vol.%

rubber toughened material, matrix deformation and yielding in both materials takes place in a very similar manner.

Figure 7. Maximum local plastic strains in rubber toughened material and fibre 'reinforced' composites.

In previous investigations it has been shown that a rubber coating on a glassy polymer sphere can be very effective in changing the stress situation from that of a glass particle filled composite to that of a rubber toughened material [7]. Because the matrix ductility is effectively used in rubber fibre composites, a rubber coating on a carbon fibre might be helpful to obtain a higher efficiency of the matrix ductility in carbon fibre reinforced composites. Therefore also a rubber coated carbon fibre composite, with a coating thickness of 1.0% of the fibre diameter, has been analyzed. In this composite material the plastic deformation takes place at the 'pole' as well as at the 'equator'. Furthermore, yielding takes place over a relatively large area when compared with that of a carbon fibre reinforced composite. With such a coating an intermediate efficiency in matrix ductility is obtained as shown in Figure 7. Because the local plastic strains are not so high as in the carbon fibre reinforced composite, a distinct increase in the composite failure strain might be expected with an increase in matrix failure strain.

4. CONCLUSION

By decreasing the cross-link density of the epoxy matrix of carbon fibre reinforced composites, an increase in transverse composite failure strain can be obtained. However, this increase in transverse strain is rather low when compared with the matrix failure strain.

Micromechanical analysis on a carbon fibre reinforced composite showed that the plastic deformation in the matrix is very localized. Due to localisation of the plastic deformation, an increase in the composite strain leads to very high plastic strains in the matrix material.

Consequently, a strong increase in matrix failure strain will hardly result in an increase in transverse composite failure strain, since at rather low strain levels matrix failure will initiate.

If the second constituent does not prevent the expansion of the plastic deformation through the whole matrix, as in the case of rubber toughened materials or in rubber fibre composites, an increase in the matrix ductility will yield a considerable increase in the material failure strain.

Numerical analyses showed that also for carbon fibre reinforced composites the increase in matrix ductility becomes more effective if a thin rubber coating is applied on the carbon fibres. Consequently, combining rubber coated carbon fibres with ductile matrices might be interesting for developing unidirectional composites with a high transverse tensile failure strain.

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